

JOINING OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES BY BOLTS AND MICROWAVE WELDING

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SUMMARY: The paper gives a contribution to the joining of thermoplastic composites by bolts and by microwave welding. It is based on two studies dealing with tests of bolted joints and the development of a new microwave welding process. Dimensioning of bolted joints and tests to examine the behavior of bolted joints for three thermoplastic composite materials with different matrices and configurations are discussed in the first section. Especially the influence of clamping by washers on the transferable loads is examined. The second section gives an overview to the microwave welding process. The potential of the microwave welding process is shown in order to get a further welding technology for plastics and their composites.

KEYWORDS: thermoplastic composites, joining, bolt, welding, microwaves

INTRODUCTION

High performance composites based on thermoplastic matrices are a well-suited alternative to steel or aluminum sheets for the high volume production of structural lightweight parts. Compared to metals they offer good weight specific properties. A one-step high speed processing technology leads to very short cycle times (less than 1 minute). Processing pressures are much lower than those to form metal sheets. This reduces investment costs for the production equipment distinctly. The efficient use of thermoplastic composites for structural applications requires reliable joining technologies to assemble parts of identical and different materials. One possibility is to adapt technologies from thermoset composites. But low-cost requirements and specific properties of thermoplastic composites require to adjust established or develop new technologies, respectively.

Joining methods for plastics and their composites can broadly be classified into mechanical fastening, adhesive bonding and welding [1]. Mechanical fastening is the most commonly used method to assemble structural parts of different materials. Like adhesive bonding it is used for joining all materials including metals. Parts joined by mechanical fastening and adhesive bonding need not to be of the same material. Welding is limited to thermoplastics and takes advantage of their ability to be reprocessed.

Basic material properties for thermoplastic composites have already been established but data related to specific applications and secondary technologies like joining by bolts are not available [2]. Load introduction into composites by bolted joints causes high stress concentrations. The manufacturing of the holes weakens the material. However, compared to adhesive bonded and welded joints they offer low cost, ease of manufacture and reliability [3]. Bolted joints can easily be disassembled but decrease weight-specific efficiency of structural parts. Large area joints like adhesion bonding or welding have a more uniform load introduction and add less weight to the structure. Concerning to costs and ease of manufacturing welded joints favor thermoplastic composites. Microwave welding is a new process and has the potential to get a further technology for joining plastics and their composites. In the first section of the paper the behavior of bolted joints in glass fabric reinforced thermoplastic composites with and without axial clamping for selected joint geometries and laminate configurations is examined. The second section gives an overview to first tests of joining thermoplastic composites by microwave welding.

JOINING BY BOLTS

Dimensioning

The design of bolted joints is based on four parts: joint geometry, fastener placement, stresses and failure modes. Typical joint geometries are single or double lap shear joints. Single lap joints bend under tensile loading [3]. For this study a bolted joint testing device in double lap shear geometry was constructed to prevent bending of the samples as source for failure. The device allows for bolt diameters between 5 and 10 mm and tests with and without axial clamping (Fig. 1). In this study only bolts with 8 mm diameter were examined.

Fig. 1: Bolted joint testing device with and without axial clamping

Axial clamping with washers improves load transfer significantly. STOCKDALE assumes a sturdy tightened preload on the washers to double the transferable load. A maximum preload increases it four times [4]. This is caused by two effects: clamping affects as delamination protection, and load introduction is changed from single form lock to a combination of form and friction lock caused by the axial compression. For the distinct creep behavior of thermoplastics the maximum preload is limited for longtime applications.

Fastener placement is critical to the load transfer into the composite part. It influences stress distributions and the occurring of failure modes. Geometric parameters for design and placement of bolted joints are the bolt diameter d , the specimen width w , distance e of the bolt center from the free end and the laminate thickness t (Fig. 2). P is the load attained during the test. These parameters in combination with the fiber orientation determine the dominating failure mode.

Fig. 2: Geometric parameters of bolted joints

A basic rule for the design bolted joints in composites says that the specimen has to fail by bearing to have well defined structural and geometric conditions. Load transfer results from the pressure on the bearing. Criteria for the design are bearing strength and notch toughness of the laminate. Bearing strength depends on fiber orientation, shear strength of the matrix and the delamination protection. 0° fibers increase bearing strength but decrease notch toughness, $\pm 45^\circ$ fibers increase notch toughness but decrease bearing strength. A combination of this is expected to reach optimum load transmission [5]. General guidelines recommend a ratio $e/d \geq 3$ and $w/2d \geq 3$ for the proper design of bolted joints [6].

Common properties determined by tests of bolted joints are bearing strength σ_b , tensile strength σ_t in the reduced cross-section and shear strength τ given by Eqn 1 to 3 [2]:

$$\sigma_b = \frac{P}{td} \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_t = \frac{P}{(w-d)t} \quad (2)$$

$$\tau = \frac{P}{2et} \quad (3)$$

Four possible failure modes appear for bolted joints in composites: bearing, tension, shear-out and cleavage (Fig. 3). Bearing failure occurs when the composite fails in compression and the bolt hole elongates. Shear-out and cleavage failures are due to shear and transverse tensile failure of the composite laminate. Tensile failure occurs when the material around the hole can not support the applied tensile loading due to its reduced cross section and stress

concentrations [3]. In general, a combination of these failure modes occurs dependent on the design of the geometric parameters.

Fig. 3: Failure modes of bolted joints in composites

Experimental

Three woven glass fabric reinforced thermoplastic composite materials with different matrices were tested: Polypropylene (PP), Nylon 6 (PA6) and Nylon 12 (PA12). For the Nylon 12 structure two configurations were available: a homogeneous laminate layer structure which was used for the other matrix materials, too, and a sandwich structure with woven glass fabric reinforced facings and a glass mat reinforced core. The materials were processed either by double belt press or by hot pressing. The bolt holes in the specimens were manufactured by a standard twist drill. Plastic washers have been used to prevent delamination caused by the twist drill.

The bolted joint testing device was installed on a universal testing machine. The free end of the specimen was fixed by hydraulic clamps. The tests were performed by a deformation speed of 3 mm/min to measure load versus deformation. The specimens are tested either without clamping or with sturdy tightened clamping. The washer diameter was three times the bolt diameter. For these test methods two typical load-deformation curves occur (Fig. 4 and 5).

Fig. 4: Typical load-deformation diagram for bolt tests without clamping

Based on recommended dimensioning ($e/d = 5$; $w/2d \geq 3$) bearing occurs as typical failure mode for tests without clamping. For lower distances w tension failure mode was also observed. The bearing and tensile stresses as well as the shear stress are easily to determine. The first peak gives the load P for Eqn (1) to (3). For some specimens the load to failure increased over the first peak load.

Fig. 5: Typical load-deformation diagram for bolt tests with sturdy tightened clamping

The specimens tested with sturdy tightened clamping failed in a combination of failure modes resulting from the complex three dimensional stress distribution in a wide area of the specimen. The load-deformation diagram shows many peaks due to the stepwise failing of the material (Fig. 5). Therefore the evaluation is more complex and needs to be done referring to a standardized method. The standard DIN 65562 evaluates as follows: the first peak yields the load of the bearing strength of the first hole elongation. The maximum peak represents the maximum bearing stress, the maximum tensile and shear stress. For the inaccuracy of this method the resulting maximum loads of the tests are compared instead of the bearing strengths (Table 1). The transferable load for sturdy tightened clamping is about twice the load without clamping due to delamination protection and additional friction locked load transfer.

Table 1: Maximum loads, [N] (8 mm bolt diameter; $0^\circ/90^\circ$ fiber orientation)

Testing Parameters	PP-Laminate	PA6-Laminate	PA12-Laminate	PA12-Sandwich
No Clamping	3180	3810	3210	2350
Sturdy Clamping	7000	6880	6530	4900

Evaluating bearing stresses following the above mentioned guidelines yields same results (Table 2). The clamped specimens exhibit the double bearing strength as non-clamped specimens.

Transferable loads do not differ much between laminates with different matrix materials. The sandwich material withstands lower loads and bearing stresses than homogeneous laminates. This results from the high content of weaker glass mat reinforced core material. Lower stress concentrations because of random orientated fibers in the core are dominated by higher stress concentrations in the glass fabric reinforced facings. Failure occurs in the facings by tension mode, delamination of facing and core layer, and by bearing.

Table 2: Bearing strength, [Mpa] (8 mm bolt diameter; 0°/90° fiber orientation)

Testing Parameters	PP-Laminate	PA6-Laminate	PA12-Laminate	PA12-Sandwich
No Clamping	198	238	200	147
Sturdy Clamping	438	430	408	306

The influence of geometric parameters and fiber orientation on transferable loads is shown in Table 3. Variation of width w does scarcely influence bearing strength but failure modes. Specimens with low ratio $w/2d$ fail by tension mode, that with higher ratio by bearing mode. Specimens having a $\pm 45^\circ$ fiber orientation reach higher stresses than those having $0^\circ/90^\circ$. The $\pm 45^\circ$ fiber orientation decreases stress concentration peaks in the hole areas. Failure sources are reduced. This emphasizes the critical stress concentrations as failure sources especially for 0° fiber orientations.

Table 3: Bearing strength for variations of testing parameters, [Mpa] (8 mm bolt diameter, no clamping)

Testing Parameters	PA12-Laminate	PA12-Sandwich
$w/2d = 1.5; e/d = 5; 0^\circ/90^\circ$	215	131
$w/2d = 3; e/d = 5; 0^\circ/90^\circ$	209	161
$w/2d = 5; e/d = 5; 0^\circ/90^\circ$	200	147
$w/2d = 5; e/d = 5; \pm 45^\circ$	230	166

MICROWAVE WELDING

Basics

Meltability of thermoplastic composite matrices allows for a variety of joining methods based on welding, e.g. ultrasonic welding, vibration welding or high frequency welding. A new innovative method is welding by microwaves. Microwaves are expression for electromagnetic waves with frequencies between 300 Mhz and 300 GHz. The microwave welding process is based on two mechanisms: polar friction and eddy current heating. Polar molecules are excited by an alternating electromagnetic field and dissipate energy by internal friction. Free charge carriers in conductive materials are accelerated and generate eddy currents in alternating electromagnetic fields dissipating energy. Microwaves heat volumetric and uniform throughout the material [7]. The interaction of a material in a microwave field is

governed by the dielectric loss property. The temperature rise ΔT of materials in a microwave field is given by [8]:

$$\Delta T = \frac{\omega t F^2 \epsilon_0 \epsilon''}{\rho c_p} \quad (4)$$

ω is the angular frequency of the field, t the time of exposure, F the intensity of the electric field, ϵ_0 the electric field constant, ϵ'' the dielectric loss factor of the material, ρ the density and c_p the heat capacity. Typical microwave generators have a frequency of 2.45 GHz. Dielectric loss factor and heat capacity are material properties and depend on temperature and frequency, respectively.

Welding Tests

Heating of pure polymers by microwaves requires a polar molecular structure which may vary in a wide range. Some polymers are microwave transparent, some absorb energy very well. In order to control the heat dissipation in the welding zone, a welding agent with well defined dielectric properties is recommended. A polar modification of the welding agent based on compatibility to the welded polymers is difficult. Possible polar additives may function as separation agents, too. Therefore, it is more advantageously to modify the agent with respect to a certain conductivity. The welding agent used for this study was modified with respect to conductivity using carbon black.

Thermoplastic composites have a low matrix content in the surface and the fibers are not weldable. To receive good welding results it is important to have enough matrix material in the welding zone. Therefore, the use of a welding agent is not only for heating control but also for the supply of matrix material in the welding zone. The welding process of thermoplastics itself is based on temperature and pressure. Pressure causes a flow of the melt for good contact.

Fig. 6: Principle arrangement of microwave welding

The welding tests were performed in a standard microwave chamber constructed for cooking. The power is adjustable between 0.34 kW and 1.7 kW. A pressure device of microwave transparent material fixes and compresses the specimens with a load of about 400 N. The device allows for an elastic compensation of reduced material thickness when molten. Three woven glass fabric reinforced thermoplastic composite materials with different matrices

(Polypropylene, Nylon 6, Polyethyleneterephthalate) were used for the examinations. The test specimens were taken out of sheets having the dimension 140 to 110 mm². The sheets were welded in single lap geometry with 20 mm overlap. The principle experimental arrangement of the microwave welding device is shown in Fig. 6.

The welded specimens were cut into stripes of 15 mm width. The lap shear strength was determined in a modified tensile test using a universal testing machine with hydraulic clamps (Table 4). Deformation speed was 2 mm/min. The Polypropylene composites show the best shear strength. Polypropylene is microwave transparent and the modification of the welding agent results in a homogeneously dissipating material. Nylon 6 and Polyethyleneterephthalat have a certain polarity disturbing the welding process. The welding agent is difficult to modify in order to achieve homogeneous energy dissipation. This is to be optimized in future.

Table 4: Average lap shear strength for microwave welded specimens, [MPa]

Material	Lap Shear Strength
Polypropylene (PP)	16.8
Nylon 6 (PA6)	12.8
Polyethyleneterephthalate (PET)	10.2

Vibration welding of the Polypropylene composite material yields an average lap shear strength of about 10 MPa. This demonstrates the potential of microwave welding for plastics and their composites.

CONCLUSIONS

Thermoplastic composites joined by bolts and tested for double lap geometry show typical load-deformation behavior and failure modes dependent on the applied geometric parameters. Clamping affects significantly the transferable loads. Sturdy tightened clamping by washers doubles the transferable loads compared to specimens without clamping. This is due to delamination protection and additional load transfer by friction. The same occurs for bearing stresses evaluated for first peak loads. Typical failure mode for tests without clamping are bearing, with clamping a combination of various failure modes. Different matrix materials have not much influence but the orientation of the fiber reinforcement. Samples having +/- 45° fiber orientation withstand higher bearing stresses than those having 0°/90° orientation. This results from lower stress concentrations as sources for failure. Additional work is to be done to get further understanding on the influence of all parameters.

Meltability of thermoplastic composites allows for joining methods based on welding. Microwave welding is a process based on either dissipating energy by internal friction of polar molecules moving in the alternating electromagnetic field or dissipating energy by generating eddy currents. A welding agent is necessary for good welding results because of heat control and adding matrix polymer to compensate the low matrix content in the surface of the composite sheets. Welding tests with a welding agent modified for conductivity showed good results especially for Polypropylene. Compared to vibration welded specimens the microwave specimens reach nearly the double lap shear strength. This demonstrates the potential of microwave welding for plastics and their composites.

REFERENCES

1. Stokes, V. K., "Joining Methods for Plastics and Plastic Composites: An Overview", *Polymer Engineering and Science*, Vol. 29, No. 19, 1989, pp.1310-1324.
2. Walsh, R., Vedula, M. and Koczak, M. J., "A Comparative Assessment of Bolted Joints in a Graphite Reinforced Thermoset vs. Thermoplastic", *Sampe Quarterly*, July 1989, pp. 15-19.
3. Benatar, A., "Joining of Polymeric Composites", *Proceedings of Manufacturing International*, Publ. by ASME, NY, USA, Vol. IV, 1988, pp. 141-153.
4. Stockdale, L. H. and Matthews, F. L., "The effect of clamping pressure on bolt bearing loads in glass fibre reinforced plastics", *Composites* 7, No. 1, 1976, p.34.
5. Bergmann, H. W., *Konstruktionsgrundlagen für Faserverbundbauteile*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, New York, Tokyo, 1992.
6. Michaeli, W. and Wegener, M., *Einführung in die Technologie der Faserverbundwerkstoffe*, Hanser-Verlag, München, Wien, 1989.
7. Siores, E., Do Rego, D., "Microwave Applications in Materials Joining", *Journal of Materials Processing Technology* 48, 1995, pp. 619-625.
8. Metaxas, R. C. and Meredith, R. J., *Industrial Microwave Heating*, IEEE Power Engineering Series 4, Peter Peregrinus Ltd., London, 1983.